

FLYING TOWARD THE FUTURE: MODERNIZATION AND COMPARISON BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AIRLINES AND POPULAR AIRLINE INDUSTRIES, STUDYING THE IMPACT OF THE AIRLINE INDUSTRY ON TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Aziza Rustamova

“Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

Tel: +998 50 007 34 07

E-mail: rustamova.aziko@gmail.com

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Abstract

This article examines the effects of the airline industry in sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan by focusing on some methods that need to be applied in Uzbekistan Airways. This research highlights the impacts of modernization and digital improvements in optimizing operational efficiency, passenger experience and its global market strength, by studying comparisons with Qatar Airways and Turkish Airlines identifying key areas for improvements such as in network connectivity, service quality staff professionalism, partnerships with tourism stakeholders. Overall, the article below gives some strategic development recommendations that plays crucial role in sustainable tourism growth of Uzbekistan and increase country's position as a key travel destination around the world.

Keywords: Uzbekistan Airways, Turkish Airlines, Qatar Airways, comparative studies, modernization, passenger experience, service quality

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the airline industry can be considered as one of the most important players of tourism, since it plays crucial role as a big bridge between many countries that helps to connect destinations and make travellers' journeys shorter and enjoyable. In today's digital era, using advanced and computerized technologies in airline industry is a key factor in this field and Uzbekistan's Air industry has a notable progress in implying these methods on its services. But, when it comes to compare with famous international airlines, there are still many deficiencies in Uzbekistan Airways airline industry such as not enough digitizing in airports and limited international influence. This article will analyse modernizing methods of Uzbekistan Airlines, and comparisons between popular international airlines, such as

Turkish Airlines, Qatar Airways and Lufthansa Airlines, as well as investigate the influence of this industry in tourism field.

Modernization in Uzbekistan Airlines

In modern aviation industry, modernization, using advanced and updated technologies plays very significant role to develop airline system. Even if there are continuous upgrades in global airlines, in case of Uzbekistan airline system there are some weaknesses and challenges that need to be solved to apply new modernization methods and meet the international aviation standards. “Uzbekistan Airways is National Air Carrier and Flag Carrier of Republic of Uzbekistan that is founded in 28 January 1992, and inherited its’ starting infrastructure from USSR main carrier Aeroflot (now the largest carrier in Russian Federation)” (Pulatov, 2024). As one of the Uzbek researchers mentioned in his research, for many years Uzbekistan airways has been using almost same and similar operational methods to manage their airline’s business operations. For example, Uzbekistan Airways uses Boeing 787-8 for international flights and Airbus A320/A321 models usually for regional routes and just because models are not modern enough and less fuel-efficient it costs a lot and they can cause emissions and noise pollutions and as a result its not environmentally friendly and need to be replaced with updated aircrafts such as Boeing 787-9 Dreamliner instead of Boeing 787-8, and Airbus A320neo as a replacement for Airbus A320/A321. The reasons to use these aircraft models instead of old ones are:

- expanding capacity: new models provide increased cargo and passenger capacity;
- saving time: no need to stop for refueling during flights to international destinations;
- reducing operating costs: flexible and modern engines reduces extra costs;
- benefits for environment: since new models more fuel-efficient, it leads reduction of CO₂.

Applying these new changes in national airline industry helps to build new modern era in this field. Additionally, except fleet modernization Uzbekistan Airways should also focus on digitization, especially upgraded booking systems, AI-powered scheduling and safety control checking’s in order to enhance passenger experience who use that airline services. As Khalikov and other researchers mentioned in their article named “Uzbekistan’s Development under the Leadership of Various Political Reforms: “The Case of Air Transport Industry””: Uza [Uzbekistan Airways] implements excessive safety control checks at the Uzbek airports reducing the free time of passengers, which they could spend at duty-free shops or eateries”(2021). As previously noted, extended security checks limit passengers’ free time and reduces their opportunities to visit duty-free shops or cafeterias inside the airport. But implementing AI-powered equipment’s like automated check-in kiosks, security screening tools with AI and smart

boarding systems can reduce long waiting times, improve passenger satisfaction. In general, the usage of digital and modern technologies, aircrafts allows Uzbekistan Airways to overcome some challenges, and optimizes passenger services, so it helps to maintain a competitive role in the developing aviation industry.

Comparison between Uzbekistan Airways and Popular International Airlines such as Qatar Airways and Turkish Airlines

Apart from technological advancements, there can be an improvement in Uzbekistan Airways by comparing it with other leading global carriers. Through these comparisons there is a chance to study the differences and similarities in passenger experience, quality of the service, network reach and connectivity and enhance its competitiveness. In terms of network connectivity and network reach there are facts that shows Qatar Airways serves more than 180 international destinations across 80+ countries and the all continents, while Turkish Airlines shows huge network connectivity with approximately 340 locations and 129+ countries which was awarded with a Guinness World Record award, when comparing to Uzbekistan Airways there are about 70+ worldwide destinations and flights are to 29+ countries in Europe, Asia and the Middle East only. With this comparative analysis it's obvious that Uzbekistan Airways has a lot to implement from leading Airline industries. Another comparison can be about passenger satisfaction, since Uzbekistan Airways is not big industry it does not have strong brand reputation and it's not featured in major global passenger satisfaction rankings and its recognition is lower than Qatar and Turkish Airlines. When it comes to passenger satisfaction Qatar Airways was named World's Best Airline by Sytrax in 2025 and its rating score is 9.4 out of 10 for passenger experience, reliability and services, when Turkish Airlines got 8/10 score in this rating (Sytrax, 2025). Turkish Airlines' goal is "offering quality, entertainment systems within the aircrafts, comfortable seats, aesthetics, and quality of presentations and investing in highly qualified personnel" (Sezgin & Kozak, 2012). However, there were some complains about Uzbekistan Airways' poor service quality and not qualified or uninterested cabin crew among passengers. Not only service quality, but employees' qualification is also crucial in this industry. For example in case study of Qatar Airways its mentioned that: "professionalism and responsibility have become a core principle in the firm. The values that are highly esteemed in the firm include loyalty, social responsiveness, cooperation with all stakeholders, and environmental awareness"(Qatar Airways 2021). Overall, while Uzbekistan Airways is in progress of expanding its network and improving their services there are so many deficiencies and national airline company needs to adopt those upgraded services and innovations to meet up with the

trends and global standards and strengthen its brand reputation and keep its competitiveness.

Connectivity between Airline Industry and Tourism Development

Development in the airline industry plays crucial role to improve the tourism sector as well. Since for the past decades tourism has increased significantly, it requires efficient air connectivity, advanced airport infrastructure and improving number of local and international flights. As one of the experts in tourism sector mentioned in his research: “The quality and ideas towards airport services impact the development of the business and tourism industry” (Shahparan, 2024). This demonstrates there are strong connection between airline and tourism industry in every country. Especially, in Uzbekistan tourism is one of the main income source and building tight relationship between these two huge industries can lead to significant tourism growth. In order to do so, firstly improvements and adjustments in airline services are required, specifically in, service quality, passenger experience and route expansion. Because “The quality of innovative services helps passengers to grow their satisfaction which is a positive point for growing the tourism industry” (Pantouvakis, 2016), similarly one of the experts in tourism industry Mohammad Shahparan had also similar argument about it, he said in his research: “The quality of airport services influences the tourists to visit again ... In the airport, it is important to ensure the tourist's satisfaction to provide quality services. If it ensures that tourists are much more satisfied with airport services it will be a positive for tourism sector development” (2024). Because of this Uzbekistan Airways should improve their service quality to satisfy the passengers: As a main element of tourism, tourists’ satisfaction has to be main focus area whenever we try to build sustainable tourism industry. Not only service quality and tourism satisfaction, but route expansion is also important for the tourism development, The reason is that if there are many direct flights from international destinations it allows tourists to use more Airline services and encourage them to choose Uzbekistan as a travel destination. In general, strengthening airline and tourism industries connection helps to set up sustainable tourism growth.

Conclusion

In summary, main essential factors such as modernization and usage of advanced digital technologies provide efficiency in operational systems and adjustments in service quality is the way to increase passenger satisfaction. Studying leading airline industries and implementing their strategies in Uzbekistan Airways by comparisons will elevate its international standing and competitiveness. Adopting new trends and applying them in real life is the best way to boost economic and touristic development in Uzbekistan.

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